

STUDY OF THE INFLUENCE OF THE REINFORCEMENT ON PRECIPITATION KINETICS IN A 6061/SiCp COMPOSITE

P. MERLE, D. DAFIR, S.M. SEYED REYHANI

Groupe d'Etudes de Métallurgie Physique et de Physique des Matériaux-URA 341
Institut National des Sciences Appliquées, Bât. 502, 69621 VILLEURBANNE-CEDEX FRANCE

ABSTRACT

Temperature-Time-Precipitation diagrams between the ambient and 300°C in a non reinforced 6061 matrix and in a 6061/SiCp composite have been established. The critical temperature under which dislocations due the reinforcement are created in the matrix has been determined from the analysis of the β' precipitation kinetics in the composite, for agings after direct quench at aging temperature. The influence on the acceleration of the coherent β'' precipitation of the microstructural state of the material (internal stresses and strains) and of the matrix-particle interfacial phenomena (diffusion, segregation of solutes) is also discussed.

Keywords: 6061-SiCp composite, precipitation, dislocations, residual stress field, Thermo-electric Power measurements.

1. INTRODUCTION

The presence of the reinforcement in an age-hardening alloy based MMC may have various consequences on the precipitation behaviour of this alloy. One may observe :

i) An acceleration of the precipitation kinetics of semi-coherent phases. This has been observed for example for the θ' phase in Al-Cu-SiCp [1], Al-Cu-Al₂O₃-SiO₂P [2], 2219-SiCp [3] composites, for the β' phase in 6061 - SiC_W,SiCp,B₄Cp or in Al₂O₃P composites [3-6,9], and for the δ' phase in 2124-SiC_W or SiCp composites [3,7].

ii) An inhibition at low ageing temperatures of the formation of G.P. zones. This phenomenon has been observed in 6061-SiCp, 7475-SiCp [3] and 6061- δ Al₂O₃F [8] composites. Despite the reduction of the amount of precipitation, an acceleration of the precipitation kinetics is sometimes observed [8]. However the effect of the reinforcement at low ageing temperatures is not very clear as in some cases the precipitation kinetics seem to be slowed down [4].

The acceleration of the precipitation of semi-coherent precipitates is generally attributed to the increase of dislocation density due to the difference in C.T.E. of the matrix and the reinforcement, as dislocations are preferential sites of germination for semi-coherent precipitates. Interfaces between the reinforcement and the matrix or lattice defects produced by their different thermal expansion coefficients, may act as sinks for vacancies. This may reduce or inhibit the formation of G.P. zones at low aging temperatures and may explain the decrease in their precipitated amount in the reinforced material. The acceleration of the precipitation of the coherent phase may be explained by the enhancement of diffusion due to the presence of dislocations or by the increase of the precipitation rate due to segregation of solute atoms near the reinforcement on the influence of the residual stress field around particles.

Apart from the classical direct observation techniques such as T.E.M., the experimental techniques used to study the influence of the reinforcement on the ageing kinetics of composites are generally hardness measurements [1,2,4-8] or Differential Scanning Calorimetry [2,3,9]. Thermoelectric Power Measurements (TEP) are being increasingly used for the study of precipitation phenomena in various metallic alloys [10]. This technique is our main experimental technique as it has been shown that it provides accurate measurements and is very easy to perform.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

Samples of 6061/SiCp composite were fabricated by Kobe Steel Company using the powder metallurgy technique. The matrix is a conventional 6061 alloy, the composition of which is given in Table 1. SiC ceramic particles (mean diameter 5 μ m) were used as reinforcement. Three different samples were studied: A : non-reinforced 6061 alloy, B : 6061-10% SiCp, C : 6061-20% SiCp.

Table 1. Chemical composition of 6061 alloy

elem.	Si	Fe	Cu	Mn	Mg	Ni	Zn	Pb	Sn	Cr	Ti
wt. %	0.65	0.32	0.26	0.06	0.81	0.01	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	0.09	0.04

2.2 Thermoelectric Power measurements

The principle of the method is to measure the voltage ΔV between two junctions of the sample with aluminium blocks. The temperature of these junctions is T and T+ ΔT . The apparatus, which has been described in previous papers [10,11], gives the relative TEP ΔS of the alloy with respect to aluminium, $\Delta S = \Delta V / \Delta T$ ($\mu V/K$) where ΔV is the low voltage provided by the Seebeck effect between the two aluminium blocks. The chosen temperatures are $T = 15 \pm 0.1$ °C and $\Delta T = 10 \pm 0.1$ °C.

2.3 Thermal treatments

To study the effect of aging kinetics on a given property such as TEP, the classical procedure used is that of cumulated aging times (C.A.T.). After a homogenization treatment at a temperature T_h , the sample is usually quenched at room temperature T_R and then aged at the desired aging temperature T_a . The TEP was measured after each aging sequence carried out on the same sample and followed by a water-quench (fig.1A). The TEP value corresponding to a given aging time t_a could also be obtained by a unique aging sequence i.e. by a non cumulative aging time (N.C.A.T.) treatment (fig.1B). In that case successive values of the aging kinetics are obtained with the same sample after a complete treatment sequence (homogenization, water-quench and aging).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of aging procedure
A) water quench- C.A.T. ; B) water quench N.C.A.T.

3. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF PRECIPITATION IN A 6061 MATRIX AND 6061/SiCp COMPOSITES.

In order to study the influence of the reinforcement on precipitation kinetics, samples A, B and C were aged after quenching at temperatures between 25°C and 300°C.

In previous works [11-12], TEM experiments allowed us to identify the characteristic TEP variations associated with the various precipitation stages in 6061 alloys for temperatures greater than 125°C. For lower temperatures, TEP variations were interpreted with literature data. Figure 2

shows four typical evolutions of the TEP of 6061 alloy samples aged at 25°C, 175°C, 250°C and 350°C. The TEP ΔS_0 of the as quenched sample is taken as a reference and the quantity $\Delta(\Delta S)$ is given by $\Delta S - \Delta S_0$ where ΔS is the TEP of the sample at time t . Figure 2A shows a continuous decrease of TEP which corresponds to the precipitation of vacancy-rich GP zones (Lutts [13]). At 175°C (figure 2B), after a very short incubation time, we observe a rapid decrease of TEP corresponding to the formation of the β'' phase. The further slight increase is due to the precipitation of the β' phase. At 250°C (figure 2C) the initial decrease of TEP corresponds to the direct precipitation of the β' phase. The following increase and stabilization of TEP corresponds to the precipitation of the equilibrium β phase. These complex variations are due to the addition of the influence of elements in solid solution and of the intrinsic influence of precipitates on the TEP of the alloy [1]. At 350°C (figure 2D), the β precipitation is very fast and the stabilization of the TEP occurs very rapidly. It has been demonstrated [12] that the following TEP increase which is observed for long aging times at this temperature is due to the precipitation of iron present in the alloy.

Figure 2. TEP variations during isothermal agings of a 6061 alloy

To study the influence of the reinforcement on precipitation, we compared the precipitation kinetics in the non reinforced matrix and in the composites for aging temperatures from 25°C to 400°C. Between 25°C and 100°C, (precipitation of vacancy-rich GP zones) precipitation is slightly modified by the presence of the reinforcement, but the complex effects which have been observed [12] will not be described here. Between 125°C and 200°C the β'' phase formation is accelerated by the presence of SiC particles. For example, at 175°C (figure 3A), the lowest point of TEP curves which corresponds to the $\beta'' \rightarrow \beta'$ transition occurs early in the composites. An acceleration of the precipitation which depends on the volume fraction of the reinforcement is also observed in the composite between 225°C and 300°C, which is the temperature range corresponding to the direct precipitation of the β' phase (figure 3B). The same effect of the reinforcement is observed in the temperature range 350°C-400°C (figure 3C) corresponding to the direct precipitation of the β phase. Moreover, the precipitation of iron is also accelerated by the presence of the reinforcement.

By varying the aging temperature in steps of 25°C, it has been possible to determine TTP diagrams for the reinforced and the unreinforced alloy, showing the effect of the reinforcement on the precipitation kinetics (figure 3D). The comparison of these diagrams clearly shows that the effect of the reinforcement is to accelerate the precipitation of the various phases and to shift their stability domain towards the low temperatures.

Figure 3. Influence of the reinforcement on precipitation kinetics at various aging temperatures :
 A) 175°C (β'' phase) ; B) 250°C (β' phase) ; C) 350°C (β phase)
 D) TTP diagrams of composite (full line) and non-reinforced 6061 alloy (dotted line)

4. INTERPRETATION

4.1 Case of the β' phase

We studied the effect of C.A.T. or N.C.A.T. treatments on the precipitation kinetics of the β' phase during an aging treatment at $T_a = 250^\circ\text{C}$ after a water quench. Figure 4 shows the variation of $\Delta(\Delta S) = \Delta S_t - \Delta S_0$ as a function of aging time at this temperature for a reinforced and a non reinforced specimen. One can observe (figure 4A) that there is no significant difference between C.A.T. or N.C.A.T. treatments. So, quenching from the aging temperature to room temperature does not modify precipitation kinetics. This means, in particular, that in the case of the reinforced material, dislocations eventually created by these successive quenches have no significant influence on the diffusion of solute elements and that the contribution of pipe diffusion, due to these dislocations, to the whole diffusion process is negligible. This shows also that precipitation kinetics are essentially controlled by the germination of β' precipitates on dislocations introduced by this first quench.

However precipitation kinetics are then a function of two parameters, the aging temperature which determines the diffusion rate and the quench temperature which determines the dislocation density and thus the nucleation rate. They cannot be related only to the dislocation density due to the presence of the reinforcement at the aging temperature. In order to have some information on this

Figure 4. Variation of $\Delta(\Delta S)$ as a function of the aging time
 -for an aging at 250°C : A) water quench ; B) isothermal quench
 C.A.T.: Matrix (a), Composite (b) ; N.C.A.T. : Matrix (c), Composite (d)
 -for an aging after isothermal quench (N.C.A.T. treatment) : C) at 225°C ; D) at 275°C.

point it is necessary to perform agings after an isothermal quench at the aging temperature itself.

However, the dislocation density created by such a quench can be much less than that created by a quench at room temperature. The germination rate of precipitates in this case should be considerably reduced. It is thus also necessary to verify if germination kinetics could be modified by the dislocations created by further quenches from the aging temperature to room temperature. We have thus compared C.A.T. and N.C.A.T. treatments for isothermally quenched specimens. The procedure is the same as previously described. The only difference is that the quench is done at the aging temperature. The reference value ΔS_0 is obtained after an initial quench at the ambient temperature of the same sample. The results are shown on figure 4B. We observe that :

i- There is still an acceleration of precipitation in the case of reinforced material with respect to matrix as well for C.A.T.(curves a and b) as for N.C.A.T. (curves c and d) treatments.

ii- In the case of the non reinforced matrix as well as in the case of the composite the minimum of the curve corresponding to the transition time $\beta' \rightarrow \beta$ is the same for C.A.T. treatments in the case of isothermal quench and water quench (compare curves a and b of figures 4A and 4B). However, especially in the case of the reinforced material, if aging curves are identical for long aging times, the initial TEP variations are less marked in the case of an isothermal quench than in the case of a water quench. As it has been shown that dislocations have a negligible influence on diffusion, this means

that, for agings after an isothermal quench, the low initial germination rate is modified by dislocations created by further quenches at room temperature. This modification is possible because the initial dislocation density is low, which is not the case for water quenched specimens.

This study shows that, if growth kinetics of precipitates are not influenced by dislocations, the germination rate of β' precipitates is very dependent on the dislocation state of the alloy. Precipitation kinetics at a given aging temperature may thus give some information on the dislocation density introduced in the material by the reinforcement at this temperature, on condition that observations are made on isothermally quenched samples aged during a N.C.A.T. treatment. We thus completed the data obtained at 250°C, by studying in the same conditions agings at 225°C and 275°C (figure 4 C,D)

We can observe that there is, in all cases, an acceleration of the precipitation in the reinforced material compared with that in the non reinforced matrix. We studied the evolution of the time t_0 corresponding to the minimum value of $\Delta(\Delta S)$ on the TEP curve, i.e. to the transition $\beta' \rightarrow \beta$. Figure 5 shows the evolution of $\log t_0$ as a function of $1/T$. The curve that corresponds to the non reinforced matrix (t_{0M}) allows us to determine an apparent activation energy of 60 KJ, but the one corresponding to the composite (t_{0C}) exhibits apparently abnormal athermal characteristics. This means that, when the aging temperature increases, the classical thermal acceleration of diffusion is annihilated by another retarding phenomenon. As already shown, dislocations essentially influence the initial germination rate of precipitates and this retarding phenomenon can only be the decrease of the germination rate due to the decrease of dislocation density when the aging temperature increases.

Thus, the extrapolation of the curve giving t_{0M} / t_{0C} as a function of temperature to the value 1 (figure 6) allows us to define an experimental temperature of about 310°C (which is outside the stability domain of the β' phase), above which the presence of reinforcement should have no effect on the precipitation kinetics in the matrix. This temperature can be considered as the temperature limit above which the recovery of the specimen occurs during quench and above which neither dislocations nor stresses are created by the reinforcement in the matrix. It is thus this temperature and not the homogenization temperature which must be used to evaluate the quantity ΔT_e necessary to estimate the amount of plastic strain and of residual stresses introduced by the reinforcement in the matrix during quench.

Figure 5. Variation of t_{0M} and t_{0C} as a function of $1/T$

Figure 6. Variation of the ratio t_{0M}/t_{0C} as a function of the aging temperature

4.2 Case of the β'' phase

As already pointed out, the various hypotheses used to explain the acceleration of the precipitation of the coherent phase are

- the enhancement of diffusion due to the presence of dislocations
- the increase in the rate of precipitation due to the segregation of solute atoms near the reinforcement on the influence either of the residual stress field around particles[6] or of the vacancy migration toward interfaces during the quench[14].

To determine precisely the influence of dislocations introduced by the reinforcement on the precipitation of the β'' phase, we studied the influence of a plastic deformation of 4% on the

precipitation kinetics in a non reinforced matrix at 175°C. This amount of plastic deformation is the one for which the β' precipitation kinetic in a non reinforced matrix is the same than that in the 20%SiC_p composite [12]. Results show (figure 7) that the β'' precipitation kinetics are practically identical in the strained and the unstrained unreinforced matrix and very different from that corresponding to the reinforced material. In this last case (figure 3A), the $\beta'' \rightarrow \beta'$ transition is observed for an aging time of 300 minutes. Dislocations have thus a negligible influence on the precipitation of the coherent β'' phase and cannot be at the origin of its acceleration .

Figure 7. Aging kinetics in an unstrained and in a 4% plastically strained 6061 matrix

Moreover, at high aging temperatures (between 350°C and 400°C), and for low aging times an acceleration of the precipitation is also observed for the β phase. In the same temperature range and for long aging times (5 10³ minutes at 350°C) an acceleration of the precipitation of iron is also observed (figure 3D). For such times and temperatures, recovery of the matrix is almost complete [12] and the residual stresses in the matrix are probably very low. The only hypothesis which thus seems to remain for the explanation of the acceleration of the precipitation due to the reinforcement is thus either an enhancement of the mean diffusion coefficient due to the contribution of the diffusion in the particle -matrix interface or an enhancement of the germination rate due to the segregation of solute elements in the particle matrix interface during the quench [14].

5. CONCLUSIONS

1- Precipitation kinetics studied by TEP measurements in a 6061 matrix and a 6061/SiC_p composite show an acceleration effect due to the reinforcement on the precipitation kinetics of β'' coherent and β' semi-coherent precipitates. Temperature-Time Precipitation diagrams established for the composite and the unreinforced matrix show that the consequence of the presence of the reinforcement is to shift towards the low temperatures the stability domains of the stable β and the metastable β' phases.

2- The acceleration of the semi-coherent precipitation due to the dislocations created by the CTE mismatch between matrix and reinforcement was analyzed by studying agings done after direct quench at the aging temperature. It was possible to determine the critical temperature under which dislocations due the reinforcement are created in the matrix. This temperature is much lower than the homogenization temperature and it is very likely this value which might be taken into account to estimate the residual stresses and the elastic and plastic residual strains in the matrix after quench.

3- Acceleration of the coherent precipitation cannot be explained by the influence of dislocations on the mean diffusion coefficient. It seems to be due essentially either to an increase of the mean diffusion coefficient attributed to the additional contribution of the diffusion in the particle -matrix interface or to the segregation of solute elements in the particle matrix interface during the quench.

References

1. Suresh, S., Chrisman, T., Sugimura, Y., *Accelerated aging in cast Al Alloy-SiC particulate composites*, Scripta Metallurgica, Vol 23, pp. 1599-1602, 1989
2. Abis, S., Donzelli, G., *Effect of the reinforcements on the ageing process of an Al-Cu/SiO₂ Al₂O₃ metal matrix composite*, Journal of Materials Science Letters, Vol.7, pp. 51-52, 1988
3. Papazian, J.M., *Effects of SiC whiskers and Particles on Precipitation in Aluminium Matrix Composites*, Metallurgical Transactions A, Vol.19A, pp. 2945-2953, 1988.
4. Rack, H.J., *Age hardening behavior of SiC whisker reinforced 6061 Aluminium*, Sixth International Conference on Composite Materials, Ed. by F.L. Matthews, N.C.R. Buskell, J.M. Hodgkinson and J. Morton, Elsevier, pp. 2.382-2.389, 1987
5. Nieh, T.G., Karlak, R.F., *Aging characteristics of B₄C-reinforced 6061-Aluminium*, Scripta Metallurgica, Vol. 18, pp. 25-28, 1984
6. Dutta, I., Bourell, D.L., Latimer, D. *A theoretical Investigation of Accelerated Aging in Metal Matrix Composites*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 22, pp. 829-849, 1988
7. Christman, T., Suresh, S., *Microstructural development in an aluminium alloy-SiC whisker composite*, Acta Metallurgica, Vol. 36, No 7, pp. 1691-1704, 1988
8. Friend, C.M., Horsfall, I., Luxton, S.D., Young, R.J., *The effect of fibre/matrix interface on the age-hardening characteristics of δ -alumina fibre reinforced AA6061*, Proceedings of the International Symposium on Advances in Cast Reinforced Metal Composites, Edited by S.G. Fihman and A.K. Dhingra, ASM International, pp. 309-316, 1988
9. Dutta, I., Allen, S.M., Hafley, J.L., *Effect of reinforcement on the aging response of cast 6061 Al-Al₂O₃ particulate composites*, Metallurgical Transactions A, Vol. 22A, pp. 2553-2563, 1991
10. Borrelly, R., Merle, P., Merlin, J., Pelletier, J.M., Vigier, G., *Thermoelectric Power for phase transformation study in metallic alloys*, Phase Transformations in Solids, M.R.S. Symposia Proceedings, Vol. 21, Edited by T. Tsakalacos, North-Holland, pp. 313-318, 1984
11. Dafir, D., Guichon, G., Borrelly, R., Cardinal, S., Gobin, P.F., Merle, P., *Study by thermoelectric power measurements of the microstructural evolution of the matrix of SiC-particle reinforced aluminium alloy 6061*, Materials Science and Engineering, Vol. A144, pp. 311-318, 1991
12. Dafir, D., Thesis, Université de Lyon, 1993.
13. Lutts, A., *Pre-precipitation in Al-Mg-Ge and Al-Mg-Si alloys*, Acta Metallurgica, Vol.9, pp. 577-586, 1961
14. Strangwood, M., Hipsley, C.A., Lewandowski, J.J., *Segregation to SiC/Al interfaces in Al based metal matrix composites*, Scripta Metallurgica et Materiala, Vol. 24, pp. 1483-1487, 1990